

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF CHEMICAL INTERACTIONS IN THE As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ SYSTEM

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Abstract

Chemical interactions in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system were studied using differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as density and microhardness measurements. A T-x phase diagram was constructed. The phase diagram of the system is quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed by the As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ compounds is 25 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$, and the temperature is 265°C. Based on the results of microstructural analysis, it was established that a solid solution region with a concentration of 5 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ is formed in the system based on the As_2Te_3 compound, while the solubility based on $TlGaTe_2$ is 10 mol. % As_2Te_3 . The physico-chemical properties of alloys of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system depending on the composition were studied.

Keywords: phase, solid solution, quasi-binary, eutectic, density.

Introduction

Arsenic chalcogenides, as well as new phases and solid solutions based on them, are materials with photovoltaic [1–6], luminescent [7,8], and acousto-optic [9–12] properties. Arsenic sulfide and selenide compounds are usually obtained as glasses, while telluride compounds are crystalline substances. Recently, semiconductor glass fibers based on arsenic chalcogenides have attracted the attention of researchers as materials with unique properties [13–16]. The As_2Te_3 compound and new phases based on it exhibit high photovoltaic properties [17–20]. A large number of materials with photovoltaic properties have also been obtained based on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound [20–23]. The $TlGaTe_2$ compound has superionic conductivity [24–25]. From this perspective, studying chemical interactions with $TlGaTe_2$ has both scientific and practical significance. We have studied a number of systems involving the compound As_2Te_3 . The As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system is studied for the first time.

The aim of this work is to study the chemical interaction in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system, construct its phase diagram, and investigate the X-ray diffraction analysis and physicochemical properties of the obtained phases.

The As_2Te_3 compound melts congruently at 381°C and crystallizes in the monoclinic syngony with the lattice parameters: $a = 14.339 \text{ \AA}$; $b = 4.006 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 9.873 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 95^\circ$, sp. gr. $C2/m$ [26].

The $TlGaTe_2$ compound melts congruently at 775°C and crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony with the unit cell parameters: $a = 8.22$; $c = 7.10 \text{ \AA}$, $z = 4$, density and microhardness $\rho = 7.32 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and 900 MPa, respectively [27].

Experimental Section

High-purity elements were used to synthesize the components of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system (As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$): As – 99.99%, Tl – 99.98%, Ga –

99.999%, and single-crystal Te – 99.999%. The As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ alloys were then prepared by co-melting the As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ components in a quartz ampoule with air evacuated to a pressure of 0.133 Pa. The alloys were synthesized in the temperature range of 600–900°C. To homogenize the alloys, heat treatment was performed at 265°C for 240 hours.

The samples were analyzed at equilibrium using physicochemical analysis methods (DTA, X-ray fluorescence, microcavitation, density, and microhardness measurements). Differential-thermal analysis (DTA) was performed using a THERMOSCAN-2 pyrometer. A chromel-alumel thermocouple was used, and the heating rate was 5°C/min.

Рентгеноструктурный анализ (РФА) проводили на рентгеновском дифрактометре D2 PHASER с использованием $CuK\alpha$ -излучения и Ni-фильтра. Микроструктурный анализ образцов проводили на микроскопе МИМ-8. Для разделения фаз в хорошо полированных образцах в качестве травильного раствора использовали хромовый раствор.

Микротвердость сплавов измеряли на металлографическом микроскопе ПМТ-3. Плотность образцов определяли пикнометрическим методом, в качестве рабочего раствора использовали толуол.

Results and Discussion

To study the chemical interactions in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system, alloys of this system were synthesized. The behavior of the resulting alloys in various environments was studied. They were found to be stable in air and organic solvents. Strong acids (HNO_3 , HCl) and alkalis ($NaOH$, KOH) decompose them. To study the phase composition of the system, the microstructure of the samples was examined. Figures 1, a, b, c, and d, show the microstructures of As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ samples with contents of 5, 25, 60, and 90 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$.

Fig. 1. Microstructures of alloys in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system.
1-5, 2-25, 3-60, 4-90 mol.% $TlGaTe_2$.

In Fig. 1, the single-phase sample of 5 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$, the As_2Te_3 compound, is predominantly a solid solution. The 25 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ sample is a eutectic composition formed in the system. The 60 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ sample is a two-phase alloy. The 90 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ sample is a solid solution based on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound.

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of alloys in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system.
1 - As_2Te_3 , 2 - 5, 3 - 60, 4 - 90, 5 - 100 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$.

To confirm the results of differential thermal and microstructural analysis, X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys containing 5, 60, and 90 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ were obtained (Fig. 2). It was found that the diffraction lines present in the diffraction patterns of single-phase alloys containing 5 and 90 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$ are identical to those of As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ compounds, respectively. That is, these samples are solid solution alloys based on As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ compounds. The diffraction lines of the 60 mol. % alloy % $TlGaTe_2$ are a mixture of diffraction lines from the original components. Thus, X-

ray diffraction analysis confirms the results of DTA and MSA.

Based on the results of physicochemical analysis, a T-x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system was constructed (Fig. 3). As can be seen from Fig. 3, the phase diagram of the system is eutectic. Solid solution regions formed in a limited area based on the original components. In the As_2Te_3 -based system, a $TlGaTe_2$ solid solution with a concentration of 5 mol. % formed. The area of the solid solution based on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound is 10 mol % $TlGaTe_2$.

Fig. 3. T-x phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system.

The results of microhardness measurements of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system alloys show that two different microhardness values were determined.

The compositional dependence of some physico-chemical properties of the system's alloys is presented in Table 1. As can be seen from the table, the microhardness value (1600–1670) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the α -solid solution formed on the As_2Te_3 compound, while the value (900–80) MPa corresponds to the microhardness of the β -solid solution

formed on the $TlGaTe_2$ compound. The dependence of the alloy density on composition is linear and consistent.

The liquidus of the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system is formed by the monovariant equilibrium curves of the α and β solid solutions. In this system, two-phase alloys consisting of ($\alpha + \beta$) crystallize below the solidus line in the concentration range of 5–90 mol. % $SrInSe_2$. The coordinate of the eutectic formed in the system is 25 mol. % $TlGaTe_2$, and the temperature is 265°C.

Table 1.

Composition, differential thermal analysis data, microhardness, and densities of alloys in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system

Composition , mol. %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, g/cm ³	Microhardness , MPa	
As_2Te_3	$TlGaTe_2$			α	β
				P=0,15 N	P=0,10 N
100	0,0	381	5,40	1600	-
97	3,0	330,380	5,44	1630	-
95	5,0	315,370	5,48	1650	-
90	10	265,350	5,59	1650	-
85	15	265,340	5,69	1650	-
80	20	265,300	5,78	-	-
75	25	265	5,88	Eutec.	Eutec.
70	30	265,410	5,98	-	-
60	40	265,570	6,17	-	980
50	50	265,640	6,36	-	980
40	60	265,680	6,55	-	980
30	70	265,710	6,74	-	980
20	80	265,735	6,94	-	980
10	90	420,760	7,13	-	980
5,0	95	570,770	7,22	-	960
0,0	100	775	7,32	-	900

Conclusion

The chemical interaction in the As_2Te_3 - $TlGaTe_2$ system was studied using differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructure analy-

sis (MSA), and density and microhardness measurements. A T-x phase diagram was constructed. The phase diagram of the system is quasi-binary and eutectic. Co-crystallization of As_2Te_3 and $TlGaTe_2$ compounds is completed at the binary eutectic point. The

eutectic composition is 25 mol. % TlGaTe₂, and the temperature is 265°C. In the system at room temperature, a solid solution region with a concentration of 5 mol. % TlGaTe₂ formed based on the As₂Te₃ compound, and a solid solution region with a concentration of 10 mol. % As₂Te₃ formed based on the TlGaTe₂ compound. The dependence of the density and microhardness of alloys of the As₂Te₃-TlGaTe₂ system on the composition was studied.

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